

What makes a Living Lab living?

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Abstract

Living Labs (LLs) have become an increasingly salient mode of experimentation and innovation, including in food policy and governance circles, and more generally the broader field of food systems transformation. A diversity of practices and concepts inform the LL model, but common features are real-world environments, multiple stakeholders and co-creation. Drawing from our experience of setting up the Living Good Food Nation Lab in Scotland, we show that a seldomly explicit dimension of LL is what keeps Labs living, e.g., the social work that goes into creating and nurturing relationships between people, communities and ideas. By applying a feminist lens to the livingness of LLs, we aim to resist this subordination of the relational dimension, and by extension encourage debate around the peripheralization of care and socially reproductive work. In turn, we hope these discussions will contribute to challenging the current paradigms and mindsets that have been impeding food systems and broader social transformation.

Key words

Global Challenges, Food Systems Transformation, Living Lab, Relationships, Invisible Work

Introduction

The Living Good Food Nation Lab (LGFNL) is a transdisciplinary consortium of academic, policy, and civil society partners working collaboratively to foster a strong, critically informed community of practice for food systems transformation in Scotland. It was established in 2023 to support the implementation of the Good Food Nation (Scotland) Act 2022, which introduced a statutory, integrated governance structure around food policy (1). This legislative framework is an innovative attempt to answer increasingly urgent calls to address the interconnected issues of malnutrition, inequalities, and climate change holistically (2)(3). Crucially, by adopting a systems approach to food policy and governance, the Act explicitly attends to the underlying paradigms that currently underpin these grand societal challenges, and which tend to be seldomly addressed by policymakers and researchers (4)(5).

Problem statement

The LGFNL aims to be a space for collective ideation and policy experimentation that brings together government officials, academics, advocacy groups and citizens. Like other Living Labs (LL), its central features are active user involvement; co-creation; and testing solutions in real-life environments (6). These dimensions are simultaneously underscored and maintained through relationships between people and organisations, but also across policy areas, values and ideologies. However, the relational work that goes into building, nurturing and developing these links is seldomly made explicit. In other words, an often under-recognised, or perhaps invisibilised, dimension of LLs is the act of making and keeping said Living Labs *alive*.

Methods

To capture, think about, and make explicit what type of invisibilised work underpins effective and generative LLs, we have taken an iterative methodological approach that builds on a series of collective reflective discussions, workshops, programme planning meetings as well as individual researchers' reflections. For the next stage of this work, we aim to broaden this process by exploring invisibilised work through a series of open discussions with LGFNL Lab partners and the wider LL community.

Early findings

From our experience of setting up the LGFNL, we found that developing and maintaining relationships at the core of our LL is a fundamentally social task, particularly when the links being nurtured are seeking to disrupt existing ways of working, wicked problems, and organisational lock-ins. In practice, such relational work is a continuous process of triggering, adjusting, and managing various stakeholders and their respective expectations, needs, and interests, using multiple modes of communication. However, we also noticed that these essential steps are seldomly treated as an equal part of the research projects associated with the LGFNL and are instead considered almost exclusively as administrative tasks. This subordination is, we argue, in part due to the association of ‘care work’ with women, and by extension its relegation within academic settings due to the influence of “longstanding patterns of devaluing socially reproductive work under capitalism” (7). We believe that by paying attention to the central role of the relational dimension, LLs actors can actively resist these patterns and foster greater creativity to address grand societal challenges.

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